

DECISIONS ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE: A STUDY OF LEVERAGE AND PROFITABILITY OF SELECTED FMCG COMPANIES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate and comprehend the impact of financial leverage on the ten-year (2013-2022) financial performance of selected five FMCG companies in India. Two independent variables have been used in this research to quantify financial leverage: debt-to-equity and interest coverage ratio. One dependent variable, Cash Profit Margin, has been used to measure financial performance. The results indicate that both ICR and DER are having negative correlation with CPM while DER is found to be having significant impact on the profitability of selected FMCG Companies. Based on these findings, the researcher recommends that the company should maintain the ideal level of debt financing to guarantee the best possible use of its assets and management should keep an eye on the interest rate associated with debt financing to prevent a liquidity issue.

KEYWORDS: Leverage, FMCG Companies, Financial Performance, Enterprise Value

INTRODUCTION

Alternative financing sources, each with their costs, are available to a company. Debentures and preference capital have a fixed bearing rate of return, whereas equity share capital has a variable rate of return. The use of an asset or sources of funding in exchange for a fixed rate of return paid by the firm is known as leverage. Every researcher wants to know how much debt a company should have to use its assets as efficiently as possible. If a company has a high debt load, there is greater danger for outsiders because there is less margin of safety for the funds. Conversely, if a company has a low debt load, the owners of the company will not earn as much from trading on equity. Thus, the company ought to make an effort to maintain an ideal level of capital structure.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Devi & Devi, 2014) researched the firms located in Pakistan to know the factors that can determine the profitability. For this purpose, the researcher took the capital structure and financial leverage, and size of the organization (on a sales basis) as the independent variables for a time of seven years (2006-2012) and a sample size of 50 companies. After adopting the least square method, it was found that capital structure had a negative relationship whereas financial leverage and size had a positive relationship with the profitability of the company.

(Malhotra & Tandon, 2013) conducted a study to know the different factors that influence the share price of the companies listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE). For this purpose, different variables like book value per share, dividend per share, earnings per share, dividend coverage ratio, price-earnings ratio, etc, were taken into consideration. The study was conducted for a time period of six years with a total sample size of 95 companies listed on

NSE. It was found that the book value of a share, earnings per share, and price-earnings ratio had a positive relationship with the share price while other selected variables had a negative relation with the share price.

(Kumar P. , 2017) researched to know the impact of earnings per share and price-earnings ratio on the market price of the company. The research was mainly focused on the auto sector and the total sample size was 8 companies. After using multiple regression analysis researcher found that both the independent variables are having a positive significant impact on the share price of the company which implies that increased profitability creates more valuation of the share price.

(Sukhija, 2014) researched the fundamental factors affecting the stock price of BSE-listed companies in India. Various variables were used in the study book value per share, dividend per share, earnings per share, payout ratio, price-earnings ratio, return on capital employed, growth, etc. The research was mainly focused on industries like auto and ancillaries, drugs and pharmaceuticals, IT and Communications, and the entertainment sector. A total of 39 sample companies were selected for research. In different industries, different selected variables have a significant impact in the case of the FMCG industry DPR, ROCE, and DPS were significant in determining the share price and having positive relationships while in the case of the auto sector book value of a share, EPS, and growth were the main determinants out of which EPS was having negative relation while in case of Pharmaceutical companies, it was found that BVS, DPS, and cover were the main factors out of which only book value was having positive relationships and in case of IT and Communication sector it was found that BVS, ROCE, and EPS were the main determinants out of which EPS was only having the negative relation.

(Sharma, 2011) in his research focused mainly on finding out the determinants of the share price. For research, the researcher undertook variables like earnings per share, book value per share, dividend per share, price-earnings ratio, dividend payout ratio, and size (in terms of sales and net worth). The reference period selected for the research was 1993-94 to 2008-09 with 115 selected companies. After conducting correlation and multiple regression analysis it was found that earnings per share, dividend per share, price-earnings ratio, and book value per share had significant negative relations with the share price of the company while dividend per share had having significant positive relation with the share price of the company.

(P.Srinivasan, 2012) researched to find out the factors affecting the share price of the company for some time of 2006 – 2011 with 6 major sectors selected. Variables like earnings per share, dividend per share, price-earnings ratio, size of the firm, and the book value of the share were used in the study. In each sector selected share price was affected by at least 2 selected variables. On a large scale, it was found that earnings per share and price-earnings ratio were having a significant impact on the valuation of the share price.

(Iqbal & al., "Determinants of Share prices , Evidence from Oil & Gas and Cement Sector of Karachi Stock Exchange (A panel data approach), 2015) researched to know the determinants in the Oil and gas and Cement Sector of the Karachi Stock Exchange for some time from 2008 to 2013 with 12 companies from the Oil and gas Sector and 19 companies from the cement sector. In the case of the Oil and gas sector, it was found that EVS, BVPS, and DPS were significant variables that helped in determining the share price while in the case of the cement sector, it was found that EPS and BVPS had positive significant relation

whereas dividend yield was having a negative significant relationship with the share price of the company.

(Rami, 2015) researched to analyze the impact of capital structure on financial performance. Different variables like EPS, return on investment, capital turnover ratio, debt to net worth, net profit ratio, return on capital employed, return on equity, etc. were taken into consideration. The time period for the study was from 2003 to 2012 with a sample size of 60 companies. Researchers conclude that there was no influence of the capital structure on the financial performance of the company while in the case of the electronic and metal industries it was found that the financial soundness of the company was largely affected by the capital structure decisions of the company.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To measure the effect of the Interest Coverage ratio on the profitability of the selected FMCG Companies.
- 2) To measure the effect of Debt Equity ratio on the profitability of the selected FMCG Companies.

SCOPE

Basically, there are two types of leverage:

- 1) Operating Leverage: The ability of a company to use its constant operating costs to analyze how changes in sales affect earnings before interest and taxes is known as operating leverage.
- 2) Financial Leverage: Financial leverage has to do with a company's financial operations. The company has a variety of options for raising money. Certain investments have a set rate of return, while others have variable returns. The ability of the company to use fixed financial costs to increase the impact of changes in earnings before interest and tax on earnings per share is referred to as financial leverage.

There is one another variation of leverage i.e. **combined leverage** (combination of operating leverage and financial leverage). It measures the overall effect of fixed operating costs and fixed financial charges on the profit available to the equity shareholders. As far as this study is concerned the researcher has undertaken the research study for financial leverage.

SELECTION AND DESCRIPTION OF THE VARIABLES

A total of 02 variables are considered in this research study to analyze the effect of financial leverage on the profitability of the company.

INTEREST COVERAGE RATIO

This ratio measures the debt servicing capacity of a firm from fixed interest on long-term loans is concerned. This ratio indicates the extent to which a fall in EBIT is tolerable in such a way that the ability of the firm to service its interest payments would not be adversely affected.

It is calculated as:

$$\text{Interest coverage ratio} = \text{EBIT/Interest.}$$

DEBT-EQUITY RATIO

This ratio measures the ratio of borrowed funds and owners' funds to have a view of the long-term solvency of a firm. This ratio reflects the individual claims of creditors and shareholders on the total assets of the firm. A high ratio indicates more risk to the creditors and vice versa.

It is calculated as:

Debt Equity ratio = Total Debt/Shareholders funds

FORMULATION OF HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant effect of interest coverage ratio on the Cash Profit Margin of selected FMCG companies in India.

Alternative Hypothesis(H₁): There is a significant effect of interest coverage ratio on the Cash Profit Margin of selected FMCG companies in India.

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant effect of the Debt Equity ratio on the Cash Profit Margin of selected FMCG companies in India.

Alternative Hypothesis(H₁): There is a significant effect of the Debt Asset ratio on the Cash Profit Margin of selected FMCG companies in India.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

This study is related to FMCG-oriented companies. The ex-post facto research is being used in this research as it involves the events which have already taken place and it cannot be manipulated.

SAMPLE SIZE

The selected sample is based on 5 FMCG companies for a reference period of 10 years. Companies were selected based on Enterprise Value which is shown below:

The names of the selected companies are mentioned below:

- 1) Hindustan Unilever Ltd.
- 2) ITC Ltd.
- 3) Nestle India Ltd.
- 4) Dabur India Ltd.
- 5) Britannia Industries Ltd.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Entire data is collected from the ACE knowledge & research portal and from financial statements of the selected companies available on official websites.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

The data is analyzed by calculating Descriptive statistics, Correlation Coefficients, and Regression. The software used to analyze the above research study is SPSS.

TIME PERIOD OF THE STUDY

Data for the period (2010-2019) is used for the purpose of this research study.

METHODOLOGY

Firstly descriptive statistics was applied to describe the relevant aspects of financial leverage and provide detailed information about each relevant variable used as a measure of financial leverage. Correlation was used to determine the direction of the relationship between different variables which are used in these research studies while regression analysis was used to know the effect of selected independent variables on the profitability of selected companies.

The model used was multiple regressions which is described as follows:

$$Y=b_0+b_1x_1+b_2x_2+b_3x_3+...+Ei$$

Where,

Y=Dependent variable of company

X=Independent variable of the company

B₀=Intercept for X variable of selected company

B₁, B₂, B₃= Coefficient for independent variable X₁, X₂, X₃ respectively

E_i=Error term

Fitting the above model into these research studies the model is as follows:

$$(CPM)_{yt}=b_0 + b_1(ICR)_{yt} + b_2(DER)_{yt}+ Ei$$

Where, ROA=Return on assets

ICR=Interest Coverage ratio

DER=Debt Equity Ratio

E_i=Error term

TABLE 1: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
CPM	16.42	5.83	50
ICR	275.29	455.38	50
DER	0.08	0.17	50

The descriptive statistics show that over the period under study in which financial leverage was measured by interest coverage ratio, debt equity ratio. The mean ranges from 0.08 for the Debt Equity ratio to 275.29 for the Interest Coverage ratio. The value of mean and standard deviation are highest for Interest Coverage Ratio which suggests that the data is widely dispersed.

TABLE 2: CORRELATION ANALYSIS

	CPM	ICR	DER
CPM	1		
ICR	-0.17	1	
DER	-0.31	-0.23	1

The correlation matrix indicates that both the selected variables Interest coverage ratio and the Debt Equity Ratio have a negative relationship with CPM which implies that financial performance degrades with an increase in debt as alongwith that the burden of the interest

also increases. Thus from this, it is implied that the company should resort low level of debt in the capital structure as it would reduce the interest-paying burden and would ultimately increase the financial performance of the company.

TABLE 3: MULTIPLE REGRESSION

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.41
R Square	0.16
Adjusted R Square	0.13
Standard Error	5.42
Observations	50

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	2	282.53	141.26	4.79	0.012
Residual	47	1384.33	29.45		
Total	49	1666.87			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	18.37	1.02	18.08	0.00	16.33	20.42	16.33	20.42
ICR	0.00	0.00	-1.96	0.06	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.00
DER	-12.47	4.45	-2.80	0.01	-21.42	-3.51	-21.42	-3.51

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

From the above table, we can see that the value of R^2 is 16% i.e. only 16% of the variation in the Cash Profit Margin is been explained by the chosen independent variable (debt-equity ratio, interest coverage ratio while the rest 84% of the variation is been caused due to other factors. Moreover, the adjusted R^2 is just 13% which suggests that the value of R^2 is highly inflated. The value of intercept from the above table is 18.37 which suggests that even if all the independent variables are kept constant CPM would be 18.37% The regression coefficient for all the independent variables is 0.00 and -12.47 respectively which denotes the slope of each and every independent variable. Moreover, if we see the p-value for the Interest Coverage Ratio is > 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is accepted suggesting that ICR does not have a significant impact on the Cash Profit Margin of the selected Companies which is also been supported with zero coefficient. While the p-value for DER is < 0.05 which suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected suggesting that the DER is having a significant impact on the CPM of the selected companies and thus company should exercise great caution while employing the debt in the capital structure.

CONCLUSION

This paper explained the study on the impact of financial leverage on the profitability of the selected companies. Data was collected from the annual reports of the selected companies from different websites for a period of 10 years (2013-2022). Cash Profit Margin was taken as a dependent variable and interest coverage ratio and debt-equity ratio were taken as independent variables. After conducting correlation and multiple regression analysis it was

found that the interest coverage ratio does not have a significant impact on the profitability of the selected companies whereas the debt-equity ratio has a significant effect on the profitability of the company. Hence can conclude that only with the change in debt level there is a change in the profitability of the company.

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ANNEXURE: LIST OF ALL THE RATIOS FOR THE SELECTED FMCG COMPANIES IN INDIA

CASH PROFIT MARGIN RATIO

Year	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	ITC Ltd.	Nestle India Ltd.	Dabur India Ltd.	Britannia Industries Ltd.
2013	17.38	30.07	16.52	19.66	14.9
2014	17.17	35.68	17.83	19.11	14.14
2015	15.09	30.09	18.32	20.52	11.42
2016	14.24	27.9	16.71	19.57	10.92
2017	14.17	20.27	15.38	19.96	10.83
2018	13.31	19.88	14.3	18.6	10.69
2019	14.06	20.98	10.73	15.05	10.07
2020	13.97	20.58	15.04	14.72	6.74
2021	14.78	19.51	15.36	14.54	5.1
2022	12.55	19.48	15.61	13.22	4.65

Source: Ace Knowledge and Research Portals

INTEREST COVERAGE RATIO

Year	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	ITC Ltd.	Nestle India Ltd.	Dabur India Ltd.	Britannia Industries Ltd.
2013	98.13	292.21	15.17	185.17	25.33
2014	86.77	239.27	18.13	74.09	30.28
2015	305.36	318.78	21.71	51.45	1115.36
2016	365.25	154.76	22.7	63.73	997.69
2017	291.73	343	21.01	62.03	934.7
2018	397.4	201.67	18	118.87	920.3
2019	368.86	179.43	248.3	99.74	730.43
2020	140.56	536.72	125.69	45.51	100.75
2021	198.13	101.88	46.96	41.74	9.8
2022	2798.6	91.83	59.37	42.63	7.63

Source: Ace Knowledge and Research Portals

DEBT EQUITY RATIO

Year	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	ITC Ltd.	Nestle India Ltd.	Dabur India Ltd.	Britannia Industries Ltd.
2013	0	0	0.02	0.03	0.55
2014	0	0	0.02	0.03	0.28
2015	0	0	0.03	0.08	0
2016	0	0	0.01	0.07	0
2017	0	0	0.01	0.08	0
2018	0	0	0.01	0.03	0
2019	0	0	0.01	0.06	0
2020	0	0	0.01	0.02	0

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2021	0	0	0.5	0.16	0.34
2022	0	0	0.58	0.24	0.84

Source: Ace Knowledge and Research Portals